

EfficientNet-Swin Transformer for Automated iRAP Road Safety Attribute Extraction in Low- and Middle-Income Countries

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Abstract

Road traffic fatalities disproportionately affect Low- and Middle-Income Countries. The International Road Assessment Programme (iRAP) could greatly benefit from automated solutions, accelerating its manual road attribute coding process for road safety assessments in these regions. This paper introduces a hybrid EfficientNet-Swin Transformer model for multi-task classification of seven iRAP attributes. A road-grouped stratified splitting methodology was applied to a dataset from Kenya to prevent data leakage, and a class-weighted Categorical Cross-Entropy loss was employed to handle imbalance. The model achieved promising results on these attributes, which demonstrate the potential of hybrid architectures for road safety assessment, yet underscores the need for strong evaluation methods and solutions to ongoing data imbalance problems.

Keywords: iRAP, Road Safety Attributes, Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs), Deep Learning, Computer Vision, Hybrid CNN-Transformer, Multi-Task Learning, Automated Road Inspection

1. Introduction

Road Traffic Injuries represent a major global public health emergency resulting in 1.19 million yearly fatalities, and Low- and Middle-Income Countries (LMICs) bear 92% of the total burden (WHO, 2023). The risk of death or injury from road traffic accidents primarily affects Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), including motorcyclists, cyclists, and pedestrians, who bear 53% of worldwide road fatalities (WHO, 2023).

The International Road Assessment Programme (iRAP) functions as a registered charity that works to eliminate high-risk roads worldwide through evidence-based road infrastructure evaluation methods (iRAP, 2024). The Star Ratings and Safer Roads Investment Plans (SRIPs) of iRAP are derived from attribute coding, which evaluates many road features that affect risk.

The conventional iRAP attribute coding system mostly depends on manual inspection of road survey videos or on-site surveys. This requires significant labor effort and leads to high costs, potential subjectivity, and limited scalability for extensive network assessments. Effective road safety

management in many countries faces a major challenge because they need comprehensive and regular assessments, which traditional iRAP attribute coding cannot provide.

The advancement of computer vision (CV) and deep learning (DL) provides an opportunity to automate road attribute extraction. Although deep learning (DL) and machine learning techniques are increasingly applied for road analysis tasks such as pavement defect detection (Yao et al., 2024) and traffic sign recognition (Sievert et al., 2022), their application to iRAP-defined road safety attributes is still relatively underdeveloped. The feasibility of using multi-task learning for classifying iRAP attributes was demonstrated by (Kacan et al., 2024). Our work extends this research by exploring a hybrid EfficientNet-Swin Transformer architecture. We hypothesize that EfficientNet's proficiency in extracting fine-grained local features, combined with the Swin Transformer's capacity to model broader spatial relationships from sequences of road segments (particularly beneficial given our 10-meter segment data), can enhance classification of diverse iRAP attributes. Furthermore, by strategically employing only stage 2 and 3 of Swin Transformer, we aim to reduce overfitting risks associated with deep Transformer models on datasets with limited samples for certain classes. A cornerstone of our approach is a rigorous evaluation methodology, incorporating road-level data splitting to ensure valid generalization and class-weighted loss functions to address inherent data imbalances.

The main contributions include:

- Evaluation of a hybrid EfficientNet-Swin Transformer for multi-task iRAP attribute classification on a dataset from Kenya, focusing on seven attributes.
- Implementation and demonstration of a rigorous road-grouped stratified data splitting protocol to ensure valid model generalization assessment.
- Application of class-weighted Categorical Cross-Entropy loss to mitigate the impact of severe class imbalance inherent in iRAP datasets.
- Analysis of model performance across diverse attributes, highlighting successes and persistent challenges, particularly for underrepresented safety-critical classes, under this robust evaluation framework.

The following sections comprise the rest of this paper. The paper reviews existing research about automated road infrastructure assessment and deep learning models used in this field in Section 2. Section 3 explains the methodology through descriptions of the dataset and the proposed EfficientNet-Swin Transformer architecture and training and evaluation procedures. The experimental results are presented in Section 4, which includes ablation studies and a per-attribute performance analysis. The paper discusses its findings together with their implications and system challenges, including class imbalance and the potential of system's practical application. The paper concludes in Section 6 while suggesting future research directions.

2. Related Work

Road infrastructure assessment through computer vision techniques has undergone substantial development over time. The initial approaches used traditional image processing together with handcrafted machine learning features for detecting cracks and signs (Yang et al., 2024). The implementation of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) as part of deep learning enabled automatic feature learning and brought significant improvements to the field (Botezatu et al., 2024). Modern state-of-the-art models implement CNNs for object detection through YOLO and Faster R-CNN, as well as semantic segmentation through U-Net and classification of road features and conditions (Kacan et al., 2024; Tardy et al., 2023; Yao et al., 2024).

The local feature extraction capabilities of CNNs are enhanced by Transformer models, which utilize self-attention mechanisms to detect long-range dependencies and global image context (Lin et al., 2020). The ViT and Swin Transformer demonstrate outstanding performance in multiple vision tasks, including several applications to road scenes (Randhawa et al., 2025). The Swin Transformer employs windowed self-attention, which provides computational efficiency alongside hierarchical representation capabilities (Liu et al., 2021).

The growing interest in hybrid models stems from understanding the different capabilities between CNNs and Transformers through their combination (Wu et al., 2024). These models combine the local feature detection capabilities of CNNs with the global context modeling strengths of Transformers. EfficientNet is a type of highly efficient CNNs that deliver the good results using fewer parameters (Tan & Le, 2019). Our research examines a particular combination of EfficientNet (efficientnet_b2) and Swin Transformer (swin_tiny_patch4_window7_224) since this combination has the potential to offer a suitable balance between performance and efficiency for road attribute classification.

The task of attribute extraction from iRAP images for multiple attributes is inherently suitable for a multi-task learning (MTL) framework. Training a model on several connected tasks through MTL aims to enhance generalization and efficiency by employing a shared representation across all tasks. (Kacan et al., 2024) used MTL with CNN backbones for iRAP attribute classification, which confirms the effectiveness of this approach.

3. Methodology

The automated classification of iRAP attributes is formulated as a multi-task learning problem where a single model predicts multiple attributes from road images.

3.1 Dataset

The research data was obtained from surveys of the roads in Kenya. A key characteristic of this dataset is its organization: image data and corresponding iRAP attribute labels for segments of each distinct road are contained in separate XLSX files. This structure where each XLSX file represents an individual road was used to split the data such that segments from the same road were not mixed in the training, validation and test sets. The dataset used in this study includes 67397 images and the images correspond to 10-meter road segments, thus offering a detailed view of the road environment. The fine details in this dataset are useful in determining specific road attributes and the fact that these segments are in sequence within each road survey provides potential for the model to learn from context.

For this study, we considered seven iRAP attributes which are crucial for road safety: 'Area type', Carriageway Label, Delineation, Number of Lanes, Paved Shoulder Driver-Side, Quality of curve, and Street Lighting. These attributes were selected due to their direct relevance to VRU safety assessment, their visual identifiability from imagery, and their presence across a sufficient number of distinct roads in the dataset to facilitate robust road-level splitting and analysis.

- **Road Grouped Stratified Splitting:** To prevent data leakage from spatially and sequentially correlated segments and to get a robust evaluation, the data was split at the road level. All image segments which belong to a single road (as defined by its source XLSX file) were assigned to either the training, validation or test set. There are 28 unique roads in our dataset with 47283 images in training, 11488 images in validation and 8626 images in test sets. An aggregated multi-label profile was constructed for each road, which indicated the presence of all classes for the

seven target attributes across all its segments. The stratification was performed at the road level using Multi-label Stratified Shuffle Split from the iterstrat library on these road profiles. This process was done to distribute the diverse combinations of attribute classes on different roads as equitably as possible across the training, validation and test splits, so that there were distinct sets of roads for each model development and evaluation phase.

- **Image Preprocessing:** The input RGB images were resized to 384x288 pixels and normalized using the standard ImageNet mean and standard deviation.
- **Data Augmentation:** Data augmentation techniques were not used for the primary results reported in this study. This is because the initial experiments with augmentation techniques such as color jitter, Gaussian blur and rotation did not yield any improvements in the final results. Moreover, this was done to get a clear performance baseline for the model architecture and the road-based splitting methodology. The effect of more advanced and domain-specific data augmentations needs to be investigated in the future.
- **Handling Missing Labels:** An ignore-index of -1 was used in the loss calculation for attributes where a label was not available for a given segment.
- **Class Imbalance:** Despite the road-based splitting which grouped the images by the distinct roads, the dataset still had a class imbalance across many of the selected attributes. Such imbalance is a common characteristic of real-world road safety data, where certain critical features or conditions are inherently rare. This imbalance was addressed during the training phase by the use of a class weighting mechanism in the loss function as explained in Section 3.3.

3.2 EfficientNet-Swin Transformer Architecture

Our research develops a Hybrid deep learning framework (**Figure 1**) that integrates EfficientNet with Swin Transformer modules for multi-attribute classification tasks. The proposed architecture uses a common backbone structure that leads to separate classification heads for different attributes.

The shared backbone uses EfficientNet's pre-trained weights because this model creates a good balance between efficiency and feature extraction performance. We obtain features from the third stage of this EfficientNet backbone. The convolutional features are first passed through a 1x1 projection layer to match channel dimensions and then sent to stage two of a pre-trained Swin Transformer. The Swin Transformer component uses windowed self-attention to process features, which enables modeling of global spatial context and long-range dependencies. Both EfficientNet and Swin use the pre-trained weights obtained from training them on ImageNet-1k dataset (Deng et al., 2009).

Swin stages output their sequences which then receive layer normalization (swin_norm) followed by reshaping. An AdaptiveAvgPool1d layer reduces spatial/sequence information to a fixed-size feature vector for each image. The pooling operation provides fixed input dimensions for classification heads while compressing the Transformer stage global information into a concise feature vector. The entire hybrid backbone received end-to-end training without any pre-trained layers being frozen.

Each classification head connects to the output vector produced by the shared backbone. The classification heads consist of a linear transformation to 64 dimensions, followed by ReLU activation and dropout with a rate of 0.5 before producing class logits.

Figure 1: Proposed Hybrid Architecture Diagram

3.3 Training Details

The model was trained for 15 epochs with a batch size of 16. The AdamW optimizer was used with a learning rate of 1e-5 and weight decay of 1e-2. Each of the seven attributes was treated as an independent classification task. The training objective utilized a weighted Categorical Cross-Entropy loss for each attribute to address class imbalance. The loss for a specific attribute a is given by:

$$L_a = -(1/B'_a) * \sum_{i=1}^{B'_a} w_{a,c_i} * \log(p_{a,i,c_i}) \quad (1)$$

Where L_a is the loss for attribute a .

B'_a is the number of samples in the batch with a valid label for attribute a .

c_i is the true class label for sample i of attribute a .

w_{a,c_i} is the pre-calculated weight for class c_i of attribute a .

p_{a,i,c_i} is the model's predicted probability (derived from softmax-normalized logits) for the true class c_i .

The class weights $w_{a,c}$ were computed based on the inverse frequency of each class c for attribute a within the training set roads:

$$w_{(a,c)} = N_{(train,a)} / (C_a * n_{(train,a,c)}) \quad (2)$$

where $N_{(train,a)}$ is the total number of training samples (from training roads) with a valid label for attribute a .

C_a is the number of unique classes for attribute a .

$n_{(train,a,c)}$ is the number of training samples (from training roads) belonging to class c for attribute a .

An ignore_index of -1 was used for samples with missing labels. The overall batch loss was the mean of L_a across all attributes with valid data in the batch.

A ReduceLROnPlateau learning rate scheduler monitored the val_avg_f1 score, reducing the learning rate by a factor of 0.5 if no improvement was observed for 3 epochs (with mode 'max' and minimum learning rate of 1e-7). Early stopping with a patience of 7 epochs was also based on this metric.

3.4 Evaluation Metrics

Analyzing real-world road data that contains iRAP attributes is challenging because safety-related attribute classes rarely appear. Weighted Categorical Cross-Entropy is used as the loss function while macro F1-score represents the primary evaluation method because it offers better performance

assessment through class imbalance. The metric gives equal importance to different classes and produces an improved assessment of model performance compared to standard accuracy when evaluating both frequent and infrequent attributes. The primary evaluation metrics are:

- Per-attribute Macro F1 Score: The primary metric, averaging the F1-score across all classes within an attribute, giving equal importance to minority classes.
- Per-attribute Accuracy: Standard classification accuracy per attribute.
- Overall Average Macro F1 Score: Mean of Macro F1 scores across seven attributes.
- Overall Average Accuracy: Mean of accuracy across all seven attributes.

The final evaluation takes place on a separate test dataset to avoid any data leakage and provide a valid evaluation of the model’s performance.

4. Experiments and Results

The hybrid EfficientNet-Swin model underwent ablation studies with weighted Categorical Cross-Entropy loss to test different configurations and determine the best hyperparameters. The experiments tested different combinations of head activation functions (ReLU, SiLU) and global pooling methods (Average (Avg), Max, GeM) and optimizers (AdamW, Adam). The remaining parameters maintained their fixed values at 16 batch size and 15 training epochs with ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler, 64 head hidden dimension, and 0.5 dropout rate.

The results on the validation set for these configurations appear in **Table 2**. The combination of **ReLU activation** with **Avg pooling** and **AdamW optimizer** produced the best validation Macro F1 score at 0.6615. The said configuration was selected for further analysis in the following sections.

4.1 Overall Performance

With validation results, we observed that the best configuration for the proposed model uses ReLU activation, Avg pooling, and AdamW optimizer, which ultimately produces the following results on the test set:

- Overall Average Accuracy: 0.8241
- Overall Average Macro F1 Score: 0.7240

4.2 Per-Attribute Performance

The best-performing configuration of the model yields the results shown in **Table 1** and **Figure 2** on the test.

Table 1: Per-Attribute Performance on Test Set (Best Configuration)

Attribute Name	Test Accuracy	Test Macro F1 Score	Majority Class Baselines
Carriageway Label	0.8496	0.8511	0.8792
Street Lighting	0.8484	0.8426	0.8053
Number of Lanes	0.9202	0.8295	0.8252
Quality of curve	0.9042	0.7177	0.8681
Delineation	0.7579	0.6447	0.7238
Paved Shoulder Driver-Side	0.7316	0.6435	0.4566
Area type	0.7567	0.5390	0.7287

Figure 2: Per-Attribute Performance Metrics on the Test Set

The analysis of **Table 1** and **Figure 2** shows different performance levels across the attributes. The Macro F1 scores for ‘Carriageway Label’, ‘Number of Lanes’ and ‘Street Lighting’ are all at or above their respective majority class baselines, indicating good learning across their classes. ‘Paved Shoulder Driver-Side’ also shows significant learning compared to its low majority class baseline.

On the other hand, ‘Area type’ and ‘Delineation’ achieved Macro F1-scores below their majority class baselines, which suggests that while the model achieves reasonable accuracy, its ability to correctly identify minority classes for these specific attributes is limited, and performance is heavily influenced by the dominant class. For ‘Quality of curve’, the Macro F1 is reasonable but still lower than its high majority class baseline, indicating challenges with less frequent curve quality categories. The inherent class imbalances within the dataset, particularly for minority classes of these attributes, create these differences in the performance metrics.

4.3 Ablation Study Summary

The results of all configurations are present in **Table 2**. The optimizer selection proved crucial because in almost all configurations, AdamW produced better Macro F1 scores than Adam. The combination of ReLU activation, Average pooling, and AdamW optimizer produced the highest validation Macro F1 score of 0.6615. Although the selection of ReLU activation offered some advantage over SiLU, the optimizer selection produced more significant variations than the pooling methods and activation functions.

Table 2: Ablation Study - Overall Validation Macro F1

Configuration (Activation, Pooling, Optimizer)	Overall Validation Macro F1 Score
ReLU, Avg, AdamW	0.6615
ReLU, Max, AdamW	0.6580
SiLU, GeM, AdamW	0.6578
SiLU, Avg, AdamW	0.6555
SiLU, Max, AdamW	0.6501

ReLU, GeM, AdamW	0.6441
ReLU, Avg, Adam	0.6236
ReLU, Max, Adam	0.6229
SiLU, Max, Adam	0.6187
SiLU, GeM, Adam	0.6173
SiLU, Avg, Adam	0.6144
ReLU, GeM, Adam	0.6129

5. Discussion

The hybrid EfficientNet-Swin Transformer model showed promising results in Kenyan road image analysis by achieving a Macro F1 test score of 0.7240 in iRAP road safety attribute multi-task classification. The model developed joint feature representations to simultaneously predict all seven attributes.

The model performs relatively well because of the synergistic combination of components within its hybrid architecture. The established local feature extraction capabilities of EfficientNet are complemented by the Swin Transformer's ability to process both spatial relationships and extended dependencies. The hybrid architecture benefits from EfficientNet's feature extraction for localized elements (e.g., evident in the reasonable performance for 'Delineation', despite its imbalance) while the Swin Transformer stages, by processing the patched representation of each 10m road segment image, can model complex spatial relationships and broader contextual aspects within that individual image's view. Although the Transformer component excels at capturing the extensive contextual understanding needed for 'Area type', this attribute remains challenging primarily due to severe class imbalance. The promising results of the model can be attributed to its component design effectively leveraging specific characteristics of the input data. The dataset's 10-meter segment attribute coding provides detailed visual information, with each image processed independently during inference. The Swin Transformer needs to model complex spatial relationships that exist within each 10m segment. Each segment operates independently during inference while training with continuous road surveys exposes the model to natural road characteristic sequences. The model develops more robust and context-aware features for individual attributes by absorbing statistical regularities and transitions from training sequences.

The system achieved good overall performance but not across all attributes. The observed variations stem directly from intrinsic dataset difficulties, which include severe class imbalance, particularly affecting safety-critical categories. **Table 1** highlights significant performance differences across attributes. The Macro F1 scores for 'Carriageway Label', 'Number of Lanes', and 'Street Lighting' were strong, indicating the model effectively learned their distinctive characteristics. The attributes 'Area type' and 'Delineation' proved challenging; their Macro F1 scores fell below their majority class baselines mainly because minority classes were underrepresented. The model's generalization abilities for these specific tasks even after applying class weighting, remained limited because some positive instances were extremely rare.

The ablation studies demonstrated that AdamW outperformed Adam as an optimizer because it delivers better weight decay regularization capabilities. The validation Macro F1 scores showed that Average pooling with ReLU and AdamW achieved the highest result although Max and GeM pooling methods delivered competitive performance in particular settings. The choice of optimizer made a greater difference than the selection of pooling methods or activation functions.

The dataset's extreme class imbalance acts as the main factor that limits the model's performance. The limited training data restricts the model from learning strong representations for minority classes. This becomes evident when using Macro F1 score, because it gives equal importance to each class.

The initial research evaluated Focal Loss as a remedy for addressing the data imbalance problem. Focal Loss demonstrated no superior performance compared to Weighted Categorical Cross-Entropy loss during the initial tests; however Focal Loss parameter optimization requires further study.

Standard data augmentation techniques involving color jitter and Gaussian blur and rotation proved ineffective in our initial tests for boosting model performance. The selected transformations either removed vital visual details required for specific iRAP attributes or the dataset already displayed sufficient natural variation, making these augmentations ineffective. Additional research is needed to determine suitable augmentation approaches that suit the domain characteristics.

The model demonstrates potential practical value but requires improvement on attributes with severe class imbalance to achieve complete autonomous coding ability. This system could ultimately operate as a supporting tool for human coders by confirming their evaluations and highlighting features or road sections requiring manual review. This system would reduce the time needed for particular iRAP assessment steps and offer the most significant benefits to Low- and Middle-Income Countries due to their restricted manual survey capabilities.

6. Conclusion

This paper presented the application of a hybrid deep learning model based on EfficientNet-Swin Transformer for automated multi-task classification of 7 iRAP road safety attributes from images in Kenya. Our findings show that hybrid CNN-Transformer architectures can contribute to improving road safety assessment procedures in LMICs. The proposed model obtained promising results with the average test Macro F1 score of 0.7240, demonstrating its ability to learn the common representations for different attributes. However, per-attribute performance varied significantly, reflecting real-world data challenges, notably the substantial class imbalance for attributes such as 'Area type'. As a result, while the overall performance is strong, in its current state, the model is best used as an effective assistive tool for human coders (annotators), rather than a fully autonomous system.

Future research directions include exploring video-based models or temporal fusion techniques to incorporate temporal context, and investigating more advanced methods specifically designed to handle severe class imbalance. Also, while standard data augmentations were ineffective in our initial experiments, further work could focus on carefully choosing domain-specific augmentations (e.g., minor weather/lighting variations, small occlusions) that may improve robustness without hurting the classification of attributes sensitive to geometric or extensive color changes. Furthermore, Selecting the frames before and after segments with a rare attribute class and using them in the training process could also be helpful and needs further investigation.

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